

soluble in comparison to II. The formation of III is a reversible reaction⁹. Therefore during heating in presence of base III is reversed to II. *p*-Chloroaniline then attacks at C-3 as a nucleophile. The intermediate so formed expels aniline to yield V (Scheme I).

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer. The mass spectrum was scanned on a Perkin-Elmer Hitachi RMU-6E Mass spectrometer at 70 eV fitted with a direct inlet system. Thin-layer chromatography was done in benzenemethanol (9:1).

3-(4'-Chlorophenylimino)-2-Indolinone¹(V) :

From I—Isatin (I) (1.47 g.; 0.01 mole), 4-Chloroaniline (1.28 g.; 0.01 mole) and ethanol (25 ml) containing one drop of glacial acetic acid were refluxed for 3 hr. The contents were cooled and the product thus separated was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 257° (Lit¹. m.p. 256-57°), yield 80%.

From III—A mixture of III (2.5 g.; 0.01 mole) ethanol (25 ml) and 4-chloroaniline (1.28 g) was refluxed for 5 min. The product thus obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 257° yield 60%.

From II—A mixture of II (2.22 g.; 0.01 mole), formalin (1 ml) and 4-chloroaniline (1.28 g.; 0.01 mole) was heated at 100° for 5 min. and then allowed to remain at room temp. overnight. The product was recrystallised from ethanol m.p. 257°, yield 55%.

1-Piperidinomethyl-3-(4'-Chlorophenylimino)-2-Indolinone⁵(VI) :

A mixture of V (2.56 g), ethanol (15 ml), formalin (1 ml) and piperidine (0.85 g; 0.01 mole) was heated for 5 min. at 80°. VI thus separated was filtered, washed with petroleum-ether (b.p. 60-80°) and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 157° (Lit⁵. m.p. 157-58°), yield 60%.

1-Morpholinomethyl-3-(4'-Chlorophenylimino)-2-Indolinone⁵(VII) :

This compound was prepared by taking morpholine instead of piperidine and adopting the procedure described for VI, m.p. 157-58° (Lit⁵. m.p. 158-59°), yield 60%.

1-Hydroxymethyl-3-Phenylimino-2-Indolinone (III) :

A mixture of II (3 g), formalin (5 ml) and water (30 ml) was refluxed for 1 hr. The product obtained after allowing the reaction mixture to remain at room temp. overnight, was recrystallised from ethanol m.p. 157-58°, (Lit⁹. m.p. 159-60°), yield 50%.

Reaction of III with *p*-Nitroaniline—III (2.50 g) and *p*-nitroaniline (1.38 g) were taken in 25 ml of

ethanol. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min. The product obtained on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 225-26°. It was identical in every respect with II (m.p., m.m.p. and I.R.). Similar reaction of III with *p*-toluidine and *p*-carbomethoxy, *p*-carbomethoxy anilines yielded II.

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Chemical Investigation of Some Mangrove Species Part V : *Phoenix paludosa*

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PHOENIX *palludosa* (Fam. Palmae) occurs in muddy maritime swamp (8-25 ft) has been undertaken for investigation in course of chemotaxonomic studies on Sundarban mangrove. Literature survey on the genus *Phoenix* revealed the distribution of Carotenoids in *P. dactylifera*¹⁻³. Other species of the genus *Phoenix* remained unexplored.

The neutral ether soluble part of the whole plant of *P. paludosa* (3.5 Kg) on chromatography over silica gel G furnished, friedelin (0.02 g), m.p. 248°, [α]_D 71°, β -amyrone (0.2 g) m.p. 168°, [α]_D +117°, triacontanol (0.5 g), m.p. 80° and β -sitosterol (3.0 g), m.p. 138°, [α]_D -35°. Salient features of chromatographic separation are described below.

First eluate registered two intense spot on tlc study. These two compounds could not be separated